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	Primary Authors	Richard CHBEIR (LIU)
	Contributors	Jorge BERZOSA (TEK)
	Reviewers	Joe CLARKE (UOS), Gulben CALIS (EGE)

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Executive Summary

Intelligent building energy management systems are an emerging field of study that is receiving much attention in recent years. Today's building is provided by a control system for optimizing energy and resource usage while ensuring occupant comfort. A common optimizing strategy is to detect room occupancies, events and activities that occur within a building. Hence, a building control system can optimize energy and resources accordingly. This strategy is proven to be effective if events, activities and occupancies can be detected accurately. In order to achieve this, several technologies are implemented. As explained in D1.2¹, HIT2GAP can use and exploit data coming from different sources (e.g., BMSs, sensors, occupants, etc.) and not only those mainly coming from BMSs (as do existing solutions). This report offers a general overview on various data sources (generated by multimedia sensors, smart equipment technologies, occupants, etc.) which could be integrated into HIT2GAP repository in order to enrich the typology and content of information and allow consequently new or complementary features in terms of diagnosis and analysis.

The purpose of this document is twofold:

- Identify existing studies, devices and recent methods to sense appropriate data and capture corresponding events (e.g., occupant activities and state),
- Pin down the lessons to learn from existing solutions, and
- Identify what is feasible and applicable/usable in the frame of HIT2GAP

in order to select the most useful technologies and methods to be integrated in it.

To do so, the D2.2 manager (LIU) conducted three main tasks related to the tasks 1.2 and 2.2:

1. Analysis of existing sensor technologies and related algorithms,
2. Analysis of existing smart devices,
3. Analysis of existing recent alternative methods.

1- Sensors

Nowadays, a sensor is not limited to a simple device (that can sense only a scalar value) but able to sense complex and multimedia parameters. Sensors are being integrated and used in a wide range of building related applications such as smart homes, buildings, and cities. In what follows, we selected several interesting solutions adopting sensors within buildings.

Scalar Sensors

In a building, several systems are mandatory for providing a basic level of functionality and occupant comfort. In general, these systems can be categorized into: (i) Heating, Ventilation and Air-Conditioning or *HVAC* systems, (ii) Lighting systems, and (iii) Electric Plug Loads Management or *EPLM* systems. Several sensor-based approaches have been provided in the literature aiming at:

- Applying scalar sensors in an HVAC system: such as [1] [2] [3] that have tried to utilize sensor networks with HVAC systems in order to monitor and minimize the overall energy consumed by the system.
- Application of scalar sensors in a lighting system: such as [4] and [5] that have tried to provide

¹ D1.2 "Technical specification of the HIT2GAP data infrastructure", HIT2GAP deliverable, October 2016.

an intelligent light control within a building.

- Application of scalar sensors in EPLM systems: such as [6] and [7] that have attempted to detect room occupancies and related activities as a way to determine whether electricity should be available in a given room.

From the existing studies and their evaluations and experimental results, one can see:

- Gathering data from different sensors, even scalar, connected to the building subsystems (HVAC, lighting, etc.), is always beneficial to detect important events and provide consequently lower energy consumption, especially when data are related to occupant activity.
- Detecting complex events (a person is eating, people are watching TV, etc.), which is precious when dealing with occupant comfort and energy consumption reduction, is not always possible with using traditional sensors.
- Occupant activity and occupancy were partially explored in existing solutions. However, including them in an appropriate way would provide better analysis and prediction results.

Multimedia Sensors

A Multimedia Sensor Network (MSN) refers to a network of interconnected sensors with at least one sensor able to capture/generate multimedia data (e.g., video, image, audio, etc.). MSNs have emerged in recent years along with the improvement of sensor device capabilities. They provide several advantages over scalar sensor networks, but mainly two:

- Providing more detailed information and precision of a given event, and
- Detecting complex events through collected data.

This requires, however, more storage and processing capacities, which needs to be considered when designing the sensor network.

In buildings, MSNs have been adopted in two main applications:

- *Building Automation Systems or BAS*: such as [8-14] and all having a common objective which is to detect events that occur within a (residential and non-residential) building accurately in order to provide suitable controlling features and thus assist occupants in their concerned activities.
- *Building Occupancy Detection or BOD*: such as [15][16] that use multimedia sensors for improving room occupancy detection as, for example, proposed by ANDES laboratory².

It is true that multimedia sensors could provide better information for detecting events, particularly complex ones. However, there are some other important aspects or challenges to be considered and solved before deeming the superiority of using multimedia sensors, in comparison with scalar sensors, in a smart building environment.

Smart devices

To overcome the limitations of simple sensors (scalar and multimedia) and the challenges of providing occupancy information accurately, reliably, affordably and without violating privacy, several dedicated smart devices have emerged in order to collect other necessary information. The idea is to use smart sensors that perform all analytics on board and output only the processed data. The

² <http://www.andes.ucmerced.edu/research/occupancy.html>

devices usually employ deep learning and object tracking algorithms that are streamlined to run effectively on low power processors. Most of them are wearable, allowing to be incorporated into items of clothing and accessories during the realization of daily tasks inside the building.

In order to choose a smart device to detect occupant activities, one must consider several parameters:

- *Software/Hardware Openness*: it is important to choose a system that allows an open and extensible framework.
- *Comfort*: it is a must to choose an appropriate device that has less impact on the occupant activities.
- *Accuracy*: it is important to also choose the device that is the most suited to complement the requirements of accuracy and periodicity of sensing.
- *Privacy*: it is a must to provide the occupant with a solution that guarantees and secures his/her privacy. This should consider different parameters (age, culture, gender, activities, etc.).

HIT2GAP Sensors

HIT2GAP adopted several scalar and smart sensors for inclusion in its platform (see Table 3 for the main list). Although pluggable thanks to its open architecture and data model, HIT2GAP platform does not include multimedia sensors mainly because they have not clearly shown yet their superiority over scalar ones.

2- Recent Methods

Various recent methods have been provided in the literature to allow better description and detection of the occupant activities.

- *Signal Processing*: Audio-based signal processing algorithms have been used nowadays to estimate indoor occupancy (i.e., number of people), due to the rapid advances of technologies to process audio and speech. The idea is to capture the changes of the acoustic properties in a room [25][26]. Recent approaches [22][23] are proposing to use vibration sensors for measuring occupant-generated vibrations (i.e., vibrations mainly produced by a person's footsteps). With this new source of information, and by extending conventional localization algorithms (to accommodate signal distortions encountered by vibrations in building structures), it will be possible to locate persons moving within a building [21][24]. These approaches also offer a means to detect and locate a person who falls, which is a significant capability in hospitals and assisted living homes.
- *Internet of Things*: IoT technologies enable connected devices to communicate with each other as well as with people, allowing for the quick completion of tasks. Many studies in this regard [27][28][29][30][31] have realized the benefits of IoT technologies to improve functionalities and provide better services for smart buildings, particularly on automation of public buildings for monitoring energy consumption, pollution level, carbon dioxide level, temperature, relative humidity, pressure, light intensity, etc. Most of these works combine Wi-Fi connectivity with ambient sensors to monitor for long periods of time indoor environments. Some of them use ad-hoc wireless sensor networks and protocols [27][28][29], while others use traditional Zig-Bee wireless networks combined with IoT technologies [30][31]. All of them consider a centralized database to store the remote collected data. IoT-based smart systems allow long period of observations, remote data gathering, reactive ambient analysis, and

further processing of historical data.

- *Crowd-sourcing/sensing and Big Data*: Smart buildings are composed of systems and devices that produce a huge amount of data related to building management or occupants. Hence, to support smart buildings, high-speed analytics are necessary to aggregate that information and here come the opportunities of Big Data. In a Big Data platform, the data flowing enables insights for patterns and correlations. Such analysis can be used to improve traditional services for smart buildings (e.g., energy savings, fault detection, automatic HVAC control, workplace optimization, etc.), and in some cases, to generate business intelligence [33][34]. Some examples of what is possible with Big Data technologies in smart buildings are: (i) rightsizing of service delivery by just-in-time triggering of work orders based on people activities, frequency of utilization, events, alarms, and needs; (ii) improved occupant satisfaction through pro-active interventions; (iii) energy savings through tuning of installations; and (iv) improved building performance by detecting trends and patterns in the collected data.
- *Social Sensors*: Social Networks (SNs) and GPS-enabled mobile devices had brought about a paradigm shift in the Internet. Location information of SN users is often given as check-in and geotagged information. Data collected from SNs can be considered as an effective means to observe and detect people activities and events within the building. For example, an occupant might tweet "I'm having lunch at home since it's raining!" allowing, after analysis, to identify his location, activity and the weather outside. This event detection need in SNs has emerged in several studies (natural phenomenon, profile detection, drawing maps, etc.). Sakaki et al. [36] proposed keyword-based models using Twitter to automatically identify where and when earthquakes occur. Yamaguchi et al. [37] used a large Twitter dataset to infer users' home locations. Crandall et al. [39] proposed a mapping system using a combination of textual and visual features from a large photographic database that was crawled from Flickr. Ruocco et al. [38] used Suffix Tree Clustering to discover events and their occurrence time and position from Flickr photographs.

3- Conclusion

Our conclusions concerning the application of these technologies to the HIT2GAP project is that several existing solutions can cope with some requirements related to the occupant behaviour and activity detection. HIT2GAP adopts several interesting sensors delivered by the partners able to provide accurate and open sensing from building and occupants (see Table 3 for more details). HIT2GAP will implement also a set of methods in which recent methods and technologies are considered mainly Big Data analysis (through a set of advanced services to be provided to end-users such as energy prediction, anomaly detection, etc.).

1 Introduction

Intelligent building energy management systems are an emerging field of study that is receiving much attention in the last decade. Today's building is considered as a *complex system*, embedding several subsystems (HVAC, lighting, etc.) and involving actors/occupants with different behaviours and needs, aiming to optimize energy and resources usage while ensuring occupant comfort. To do so, several data sources need to be analyzed, but mainly:

- Data about buildings (physical features, purpose, etc.),
- Data about building equipment (lighting, temperature, heating, etc.),
- Data about activities and occupancy (events, number of people, etc.),
- Data about occupants (interests, preferences, etc.).

Data related to buildings and equipment has been exploited in most of the existing optimization solutions. However, they have some common limitations related to individual needs of occupants (which are heterogeneous) and their various activities, which cannot be treated as a whole. A better optimizing strategy is to detect the activities occurring within a building in order to fine-tune energy and resources usage. This strategy is proven to be effective if events, activities and occupancies can be detected accurately. In order to achieve this, new sensors, smart devices, and related technologies play a crucial role in data gathering and detecting events that can be found within a building.

To answer those questions and challenges, we explored several new technologies and studies in the literature. In what follows, we detail them.

1.1 Purpose

The purpose of this document is twofold:

- Identify existing studies, devices and recent methods related to capturing occupant activities and events,
- Pin down the lessons to be learned from existing solutions, and
- Identify what is feasible and applicable/usable in the frame of HIT2GAP

in order to select the most useful technologies and methods to be integrated in it.

1.2 Organization of work

In order to write the deliverable D2.2, LIUPPA (LIU), with the help of TEKNIKER, conducted an analysis of existing solutions and approaches. Some are provided currently in the literature and connected to our project from different perspectives (sensors, occupants, etc.), while others are currently/previously conducted by TEKNIKER.

1.3 Contributions of partners

LIU has structured this report and coordinated the collection of information from the different partners involved in this task of the HIT2GAP project. Except Section 3 which is provided by TEKNIKER, all the other sections have been written by LIU.

1.4 Report structure

This deliverable is structured as follows:

- Initially, an **Executive Summary** of the work is provided.
- An **Introduction** is also provided to describe the context and organization of this work.
- **Section 2** is dedicated to related work in detecting the building activities and occupancy using scalar and multimedia sensors as well as existing smart devices.
- **Section 3** details recent methods related to vibration detection, signal processing, IoT, big data analysis, crowdsourcing, and social sensors.
- **Section 4** concludes this report by providing an analysis of the mapping between existing solutions and the HIT2GAP approach.

2 Sensors

Sensor is originally a term referring to a component of measuring system that is used for measuring a given quantity [40]. With the introduction of Internet of Things, however, sensor is now broadly referred to any physical or virtual entities capable for generating data [41]. Sensors can be limited to simple devices, we call them in this report scalar sensors, that can sense only a scalar value (such as air flow meter, water meter, inclinometer, velocity receiver, RFID, infrared thermometer, motion detector, etc.), or include wide range of sophisticated/smart devices (such as smartphones, tablets, laptops, etc.). They can also be multimedia based (e.g., video, audio or image sensors) able to sense complex and multimedia data. All of them are being integrated tightly in a wide range of building related applications such as smart home automation, smart building, or smart city [20]. In what follows, we detail several interesting approaches in order to observe how they have been adopted to manage energy efficiency and/or detect complex events in a smart building.

2.1 Scalar sensors

The advances of “smart” technologies and equipment led to a great improvement in sensor technologies. A scalar sensor (or actuator) can detect and measure a physical property. Nowadays, the sensor technologies continue evolving to reach more and more complex requirements in various application domains. In this regard, we wanted to explore and study how these technologies have been adopted and used in smart buildings, since some can be added/plugged without the BMS, in order to measure energy usage and occupant comfort. To do so, sensors can be whether used to detect/automate some actions (window/door opening/closing, human presence detection, etc.) or embedded into the following systems: (i) Heating, Ventilation and Air-Conditioning (or *HVAC*) systems, (ii) Lighting systems, and (iii) Electric Plug Loads Management (or *EPLM*) systems. In this context, many sensor manufacturers propose new advances on sensor hardware to be most cost-effective and also more competitive. Several sensor-based applications are worthy to mention and will be detailed in what follows.

2.1.1 Application of scalar sensors in an HVAC system

An HVAC system is a system that is used for controlling the indoor environmental comfort. The ultimate goal of an HVAC system is to provide occupants an ideal indoor environment (thermal, acoustic, visual comfort and air quality). Several interesting works have tried to utilize sensor networks with HVAC systems in order to monitor and minimize the overall energy consumed by the system. The main ones are summarized in the following subsections.

2.1.1.1 Minimizing HVAC energy consumption using a wireless sensor network [1]

This work aims at applying a Wireless Sensor Network (WSN) to minimize the energy consumption of an HVAC system. The proposed block diagram of an HVAC control system is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Block diagram of an HVAC control system as proposed in [1]

In short, the proposed HVAC control system consists of 2 parts: a *monitoring system* and *actuators*. A monitoring system is a collection of wireless sensor nodes: external sensors nodes and zone sensor nodes. External sensor nodes are used for collecting weather conditions outside a given building. They usually include: temperature sensors, light sensors, and relative humidity sensors. Zone sensor nodes are used for monitoring indoor thermal conditions. They usually include: temperature sensors, occupancy sensors (an infrared sensor for detecting occupant presence), and relative humidity sensors. Actuators are devices performing the automatic control and regulation of the HVAC systems (heating distribution, ventilation,). They react per readings provided by a monitoring system.

Sensors of the proposed HVAC control system are assumed to be all scalar and the collected data features are indoor temperature, wall temperature, roof temperature, external temperature, indoor relative humidity, outdoor relative humidity and room occupancy data. A framework for computing appropriate outputs for actuators is also proposed in [1]. It assumes a centralized computation of all sensor readings by a main controller (see Figure 1). The framework is validated by means of simulations. The simulations were carried out by using an analytical model for a building thermal zone. It is given as follows:

$$T(s) = G_2(s) [\beta T_{sup}(s) + 2\gamma G_{w1}(s)[T(s) + T_o(s)] + 2\delta G_{w2}(s)[T(s) + T_o(s)] + \lambda G_R(s)[T(s) + T_o(s)]] \quad (1)$$

Equation (1) is a transfer function of a building thermal zone. It is developed under 4 assumptions:

1. The zone walls and roof have identical effect on the zone temperature while the ground effect is negligible.
2. The density of the air is constant.
3. Interzone pressure losses are negligible.
4. External heat sources such as human bodies and appliances are simulated as an uncontrolled input.

Two sets of parameter values are used for the simulation. The first set represents a hot day (the external temperature is above 40°C). The other set represents a moderately hot day (the external temperature is above 32°C). The obtained results have shown more than 50% energy savings in highly occupied rooms comparing to a normal HVAC system.

2.1.1.2 Energy-efficient control of under-actuated HVAC zones in commercial buildings [2]

This work proposes an occupancy-based feedback control method for an HVAC system. In short, the method uses room occupancy information and sensor readings to adapt outputs of HVAC related appliances accordingly. Sensors used in this work are CO₂ sensors, temperature sensors, relative humidity sensors and motion sensors. The proposed method assumes that all sensor readings are gathered in a centralized database (as in [1]). To validate the proposed schema, the authors deployed sensor nodes and a programmable HVAC system in the University of Florida's Pugh Hall (a building with 40,000 square feet of floor space). 5 rooms were selected for experiment, 3 high occupancy rate rooms and 2 low occupancy rate rooms. The experiments were conducted during a winter period where heating energy is highly demanded. The obtained results have shown significant energy savings rate (between 29 – 80% depending on room occupancy level). 50% of the total energy saving mainly came from the heating system.

2.1.1.3 HVACMeter: apportionment of HVAC power to thermal zones and air handler units [3]

HVACMeter is a system for estimating both heating and cooling energy required within a given thermal zone. Sensors used within this system are occupancy and indoor temperature sensors. Temperature sensors and airflow volume sensors are also installed within the HVAC control units within a building. The provided system takes historical sensor readings and calculates the heating and cooling energy estimation using a mathematical model. To validate the HVACMeter system, the author deployed the system into 3 buildings in the University of California, San Diego campus. The fundamental parameters that were chosen for the HVACMeter to control are the air temperature and the air volume. The experimental results have shown 44.5% average Root Mean Square Error (RMSE).

2.1.1.4 Demand-driven HVAC

HVAC automatic control have been a subject in the context of smart buildings from the last decade based on scalar sensors and traditional approaches. In traditional HVAC operations, the ventilation and conditioning demand is assumed to be at the peak based on maximum occupancy during operational hours, and the temperature and humidity are used as the sole inputs in adjusting the operations, which often results in waste of HVAC related energy consumption [56]. Currently, the new tendency is on demand-driven HVAC operations to reduce HVAC related energy consumption. Demand-driven HVAC operations replace the assumption that the ventilation and conditioning demand is at the peak with the actual demand based on real-time sensing of the environment. This tendency relies on the availability of occupancy information to detect and track multiple stationary and mobile occupants in multiple spaces simultaneously, which allows to determine peak/off-hour modes that impact cooling/heating loads of HVAC systems (i.e., for determining the heating and cooling loads) [57]. Thus, occupancy information enables timely reaction to changing ventilation and

conditioning demands, and minimizes energy consumption without compromising the occupant comfort [58-61].

A thermal zone is an individual indoor space or group of neighboring spaces with similar thermal loads, and typically served by a dedicated HVAC subsystem. Occupants are detected in each room by sensors and may wirelessly communicate to a zonal compiler that determines zonal occupancy. The zonal occupancy count is transmitted to an interface relay that immediately adjusts the intensity and rate of the specific utility [58-61]. In order to provide effective occupancy detection in thermal zones for demand-driven HVAC systems, the most recent works are based on detecting the CO₂ concentration, sensing movement of occupants with Passive Infrared (PIR) sensors, and detecting location and activities of occupancy with Radio Frequency Identification Devices (RFID). Some of these works are revised below.

Works based on the use of carbon-dioxide (CO₂) sensors [57,62-67] offer the capability to provide count of occupants as well as the ability to provide information on the indoor air quality. However, these approaches present drawbacks related to the count of occupants based on estimates, the considerable time to produce results, and the affectation of CO₂ concentration by external conditions such as variations in wind speed, intermittent opening, and closing of windows/doors. All these constraints limit their use for demand-driven HVAC due to the impossibility of providing accurate and real-time occupancy information. Same is true for other recent works based on PIR sensors provided to develop occupancy detection systems [73-76].

Since the limitations of all these approaches, solutions must combine several of them, considering the balance between accuracy and cost/effectivity. In particular, RFID technology can provide adequate accuracy; it is cost efficient; it does not require line of sight conditions; it has on-board data storage capacity that can be used for another purpose such as building asset management; and it is widely used by the construction industry so that hardware can be shared by multiple tasks.

2.1.2 Application of scalar sensors in a lighting system

A lighting system is considered as one of the most important systems within a building. The Digital Addressable Lighting Interface (DALI)³ is an International Standard (IEC 62386) for the control of electronic ballasts, transformers, LED's, emergency lights, and exit signs in an easy to manage digital lighting control system. A DALI-based control system can provide a complete building-wide digital lighting control system, consisting of DCBM-DALI Line Controllers linked on an Ethernet network, which allow to scale the lighting system from a room, to a floor, to a building, and beyond. Each Line Controller uses time schedules, pushbuttons, switches, and sensors to control lighting and emergency lights on DALI Lines.

Sensor networks can be applied to help monitor and optimize the usage of such systems (whether they are DALI-based or not). Several related studies have tried to provide intelligent light control within a building. We selected 3 significant ones as detailed below.

2.1.2.1 Intelligent light control using sensor networks intelligent light control using sensor networks [4]

This study [4] is one of the earliest that focused on the intelligent light control system within a building. A strategy for controlling light is proposed here and called "daylight harvesting". The proposed

³ <http://www.dali-ag.org/discover-dali/dali-applications.html>

system aims to light up necessary zones automatically when required and when external daylight is not bright enough. To do so, light and motion sensors are deployed within a building. Light level, motion information, and room occupancy information (provided by motion sensors) are gathered in a centralized way to determine which zones of the building require light. To validate the system, an experiment was carried out in a physical testbed. The testbed was a room that contained 10 dimmable lamps. A light sensor node was installed on every lamp. The sensor readings were sent to a desktop PC that was acting as a control unit. The control unit evaluated all the readings and sent commands back to each sensor node to adjust the luminosity of each lamp according to the daylight harvesting strategy. The result showed a 25% reduction in total energy usage.

2.1.2.2 A low cost, highly scalable wireless sensor network solution to achieve smart LED light control for green buildings [5]

A LED bulb consumes in general less energy than a normal light bulb. Hence, lots of current buildings choose to change all bulbs into LED ones. Thus, existing light control systems need to be updated accordingly to provide better support for LED bulb features (mainly tuneable brightness level). The work in [5] is one of the latest that focuses on intelligent LED light control system in a building. It assigns WSN nodes to every LED bulb within a building in the aim of observing current brightness level and motion within the rooms. A technique is provided to prioritize external daylight in the same manner of [4]. It is designed specifically for LED bulbs, thus it also allows the adjustment of brightness level of each bulb for further energy savings. The work has been validated in a building under a real-life usage scenario. Wireless sensor nodes are attached to every indoor LED light bulb of the VerdeLED⁴ company office. The results have shown a reduction of 55% energy consumption over a 6-month span.

2.1.2.3 Controlling lighting systems with PIR sensors

In principle, PIR sensors detect the energy given off by objects within its view and are commonly used in occupancy detection systems for demand driven control applications, particularly in the control of lighting systems [59,61,73]. PIR sensors have been demonstrated to provide fine-grained occupancy information on user presence [74,76] and location [75]. However, their application in buildings is somewhat limited to occupant driven control of lighting systems due to their binary output [59,61] making them inappropriate to provide information on count, which is an essential property required for other applications (such as demand controlled ventilation). Additionally, PIR sensors can report false output, due to the presence of heat currents from HVAC systems or when having continuous motion.

2.1.3 Application of scalar sensors in EPLM systems

Plug load refers to the energy that a given electronic appliance consumes through an electric plug within a building. One of the possible strategies for optimizing energy usage is to decide which plug requires electricity. To do so, sensor networks are commonly applied to detect room occupancies and related activities in a way that allows determination of whether electricity should be distributed in a given room. In the following, we present 2 significant works.

⁴ <http://www.verdeled.com/>

2.1.3.1 Distributed wireless control for building energy management [6]

This study focuses on automated building energy control. It utilizes sensor networks to determine the occupancies and activities in each room within a building. Sensors that are used include motion sensors, door sensors, and ambient light sensors. Sensor readings are sent to an energy controller unit which is installed within every room. A rule-based control algorithm is proposed for an energy controller to determine if it is necessary to provide electricity to electric plugs within a room. The experimental prototype of the system had been installed into 2 offices within a building. Door sensors and PIR sensors had been installed in both offices. One rule-based control system was installed in every office. The example of the rule can be seen as follows.

```
if door open then
  // room is occupied
  setRelay(close)
else
  // assess occupancy
  count = 0
  for 60 seconds do
    wait for motion event or timeout
    count += 1
  end for
  if count ≥ 5 then
    // room is occupied
    setRelay(close)
  else
    // room is not occupied
    setRelay(open)
  end if
end if
```

Figure 2: Example of the rule for detecting occupancy information

As seen in Figure 2, the rule relies on the detection of the door and PIR sensors. The results have shown 7.1% to 14.6% energy saving despite a relatively simple rule-based control system adopted in the experiments.

2.1.3.2 WSN-based smart sensors and actuator for power management in intelligent buildings [7]

This work proposes to monitor the electric energy consumption for each electric appliance. To do so, the authors developed an electric consumption sensor (silver box in Figure 3) to monitor and record the electric energy consumption data.

Figure 3: Electric consumption sensors

The sensors served as intermediates between electric appliances and electric plugs. The electric consumption usage data were monitored and sent to a central monitor unit through wireless connection. The contribution of this study does not really rely on the minimization of energy consumption but rather on the architecture of electric consumption monitoring system.

2.1.4 Discussion

As one can see from the existing studies:

- Gathering data from different sensors, even scalar, connected to the building subsystems (HVAC, lighting, etc.), is always beneficial to detect important events and provide consequently lower energy consumption, especially when data are related to occupant activity
- Detecting complex events (a person is eating, people are watching TV, etc.), which is precious when dealing with occupant comfort and energy consumption reduction, is not always possible with using scalar sensors.
- Occupant activity and occupancy were partially explored in existing solutions. However, including them in an appropriate way would provide better analysis and prediction results.

This is what we are willing to do in HIT2GAP:

- Adding more data inputs and readings from ALL the building subsystems so as to shape the building energy signature and increase event coverage.
- Adding more features related to occupant activities.
- Being able to detect complex events in the buildings.

2.2 Multimedia sensors

A Multimedia Sensor Network (MSN) refers to a network of interconnected sensors with at least one sensor able to capture/generate multimedia data (e.g., video, image, audio, etc.). In essence, MSNs have emerged in recent years along with the improvement of sensor device capabilities. They provide several advantages over scalar sensor networks, but mainly two of them can be highlighted here:

- Providing more detailed information and precision of a given event, and
- Detecting complex events through collected data.

This requires, however, more storage and processing capacities, which needs to be considered when designing the sensor network.

In buildings, MSNs have been adopted in two main categories: in *Building Automation Systems or BAS* [8-14] and in *Building Occupancy Detection or BOD* [15][16]. In the following, we briefly present several of these studies related to both building automation and building occupancy detection applications. It is to be noted that the main aim of the following studies is not directly related to energy efficiency but more addressing the sensing of complex events in buildings but can indirectly help to detect the occupant activities.

2.2.1 Application of multimedia sensors in BASs

Most of the studies have integrated MSNs in a BAS [8-14]. Their common objective was to detect events that occur within a (residential and non-residential) building accurately in order to provide suitable controlling features and thus assist occupants in their concerned activities. In the following, we briefly present main studies in this category.

2.2.1.1 Sweet Home [10]

The Sweet Home project [10] focuses on the development of a Home Automation System (HAS). Its goal is twofold:

- Detect activities and events that occur within a home using audio sensors.
- Allow occupants to communicate with the HAS using voice commands. For instance, “Turn the light on/off”, “Call Mr...” or “Call ambulance”. All the voice commands are recorded in the French language.

The list of sensors adopted in [10] are:

- *Multimedia Sensors*: video cameras and microphones.
- *Scalar Sensors*: PIR sensors, door/window contact sensors, temperature sensors, CO₂ sensors, power usage sensors, and water usage sensors.

Using such sensors, the following events were detected: *Sleeping, Resting, Eating, Hygiene, Using Toilet, Dress/Undress and phoning.*

The authors do not propose a real-time or a near-real time detection technique for a live deployment setting. Instead, they use a pre-recorded data corpus gathered from an experimental apartment. The corpus is called the “Sweet Home”. To detect the aforementioned events, they use a Support Vector Machine (SVM) to classify occupant activities via extracted voices and indoor spatio-temporal positions. The results have shown that occupants’ events can be detected with an average accuracy of 86.8%.

It is to be noted that this study presents several advantages. First, sensors used in it are diverse, which is common in most of the smart home cases. The Sweet Home corpus, developed by the authors, can also be used for various building applications. For instance, it can be used for developing an energy optimizing system since power usage and water usage are also recorded within the corpus. However, the algorithm proposed in [10] has not yet been deployed in a real life scenario.

2.2.1.2 Audio event detection using adaptive feature extraction scheme [17]

The recent study proposed in [17] consists of detecting events within audio data. It uses the “Office Live” corpus provided in [18], which is a dataset of sounds recorded via microphones located in an actual office. The following events were detected: *Announcement/Alert, Cough, Drawer opening/closing, Keyboard/mouse usage, Table knocking, Laughing, Turing pages (of books or paper report), Pen drop, Telephoning, Printing, Speaking, and switches (e.g., light switch)*.

To do so, the proposed approach extracts the dominant frequency and Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCC) features of each audio event and trains them by using an SVM learner. The results have shown that the accuracy of detecting each of the aforementioned events is high approximating 72%. The only problem of this study is that it does not consider any aspect related to real-time or near-real-time processing deployment.

2.2.2 Application of multimedia sensors in BOD

The usage of multimedia sensors within a smart building to solve issues related to energy management has not yet been widely adopted. Multimedia sensors may not be suitable in a residential building because they are mainly too intrusive for occupants’ privacy [19]. However, it is accepted nowadays in non-residential buildings (e.g., commercial building, university building, etc.) since buildings and rooms are commonly equipped with a network of surveillance sensors (e.g., cameras). Many works propose various video based systems [68-72], which detect the occupancy in a monitored space by using image-processing techniques. We describe several interesting studies that use multimedia sensors for improving room occupancies detection below.

2.2.2.1 OBSERVE: Occupancy-Based System for Efficient Reduction of HVAC Energy [16]

OBSERVE [16] chooses to detect room occupancies from a network of video cameras. It addresses one of the limitations of scalar sensors (e.g., PIR sensors) for detecting occupancy in a precise way. For instance, they cannot be used easily for detecting the number of occupants, their movement, a movement trajectory of one occupant, etc. Hence, OBSERVE proposes the usage of a wireless

camera-based sensor network for detecting such information and adapting the HVAC control system accordingly.

Using such sensors, OBSERVE can detect the following events: *Area Occupied*, *Area unoccupied*, *Occupant moves to another area*, *number of occupants within a given area*.

OBSERVE uses 'Smart Camera Occupancy Position Estimation System' (SCOPEs) [9] for managing 16 wireless camera nodes that are used for capturing a mobility pattern of occupants and constructing a floor plan from such information. The illustration of SCOPEs and the constructed floor plan can be seen in

Figure 4.

Figure 4: Occupancy areas and a sample camera snapshot from the SCOPEs

Figure 4-a shows a floor plan of occupancy areas constructed by SCOPEs. The areas that are highlighted in grey are occupancy areas. The red lines within the figure indicate a transition point (a point that occupants use to move from one area to another area).

Figure 4-b shows a snapshot of a real-time image captured by SCOPEs. Red lines and green lines within the image are used to indicate transition boundaries. SCOPEs counts the number of occupants and their movement trajectory by using the object-background subtraction technique⁵.

The OBSERVE system takes the number of occupants, locations and movement trajectories as detected from the SCOPEs, and proposes three data models for modelling room occupancies:

- The first model is a multivariate Gaussian model. It allows to predict room occupancy by fitting data with multivariate Gaussian distribution.
- The second model is the agent-based model. It is used for predicting occupants' mobility pattern (e.g., movement direction prediction). The prediction is done using a heuristic prediction from occupants' movement trajectories information.
- The final model is the Markov chain model.

The energy saving potential of OBSERVE in optimizing the HVAC system has been evaluated by means of simulation. The obtained results have shown that the annual energy saving can reach an average of 42%. It is to be noted nonetheless that the energy saving could be improved since a wireless camera used in OBSERVE consumes a lot of electric power. Thus, it is hard to operate these sensors with batteries. The significant accuracy improvement is also questionable when

⁵ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Background_subtraction

comparing with a scalar sensor based system that may provide less accurate detection but can work better under low power condition.

2.2.2.2 Power efficient Occupancy based Energy Management system (POEM) [15]

The aim of POEM [15] is to further improve the energy management proposed in OBSERVE [16]. Hence, the context of the development of POEM is similar to OBSERVE. However, POEM chooses to use a combination of scalar sensors and multimedia sensors in order to provide better room occupancies detection. Thus, POEM uses the following sensors:

- Multimedia sensors: wireless cameras.
- Scalar sensors: PIR sensors.

In order to detect the following events: *Area Occupied, Area unoccupied, Occupant moves to another area, and number of people within a given area.*

To do so, POEM uses an improved version of SCOPES called OPTical Turnstile NETwork (OPTNET) [15]. In essence, OPTNET employs a fast-lightweight human motion detection and area transition technique. The movement trajectories of occupants are represented as a vector. In order to detect and predict the occupancy level within a building, this vector is compared to known labelled data by using l-Nearest Neighbours (KNN) algorithm. The scalar sensor network used in POEM is called 'Binary Occupancy Network' (BONET), which is a wireless PIR sensor network for detecting occupants' presence. The energy optimizing strategy of POEM is to schedule the HVAC system in order to match the likely arrival of occupants. The detection from both OPTNET and BONET is combined to determine actual occupancy information within a building. The results of POEM have shown that:

- OPTNET alone can predict building occupancy with 94% accuracy.
- By combining OPTNET with BONET, the accuracy can be improved further. The occupancy estimation error when combining both OPTNET and BONET together is reduced to an average of 1.83 persons.

This has been validated on an actual test-bed and the energy saving estimation was annually approximately to 30%. However, like OBSERVE, the energy required for operating a wireless camera sensor network is still a disadvantage.

2.2.3 Discussion

It is true that multimedia sensors have not been used up to now directly for energy efficiency. However, one can see that they provide better information for detecting events, particularly complex ones. To do that properly, there are several important aspects or challenges to be considered and solved before deeming the superiority and feasibility of using multimedia sensors, in comparison with scalar sensors, in energy efficiency context of a smart building environment. To compare the features of scalar and multimedia sensors, we suggest the following criteria: supported event type, precision, intrusiveness, cost, and energy consumption. The comparison result is summarized in

Table 1. Briefly, PIR sensors and contact sensors are generally 'binary' since the result of their detection is a Boolean value (e.g., true or false, on or off). Temperature sensors, CO₂ sensors, power

usage sensors and water usage are digital as they produce numerical values as an output. Concerning the precision, intrusiveness, price, energy consumption, all scalar sensors share the same features: high precision, low intrusiveness, low price processing, and low energy consumption. Also, most of them are mainly connected to the building, except PIR and contact sensors.

Table 1: Sensor features evaluation

		Supported Event Type	Precision	Intrusiveness	Cost	Energy Consumption	Processing	Data
Multimedia	Camera	Various	Various	High	Medium	High	High	Building/Occupant
	Microphone	Various	Various	High	Medium	High	High	Building/Occupant
Scalar	PIR	Binary	High	Low	Low	Low	Low	Occupant
	Contact Sensor	Binary	High	Low	Low	Low	Low	Occupant
	Temperature Sensor	Numerical	High	Low	Low	Low	Low	Building
	CO ₂ Sensor	Numerical	High	Low	Low	Low	Low	Building
	Power Usage Sensor	Numerical	High	Low	Low	Low	Low	Building
	Water Usage Sensor	Numerical	High	Low	Low	Low	Low	Building

Concerning multimedia sensors, such as a camera and a microphone sensor, they can detect various kinds of events with various precision depending on the used multimedia algorithms. They can also be connected to both the building and the occupants. The intrusiveness can be considered as high due to the privacy concern. The requested hardware cost, in addition to the large storage space, is significantly higher than scalar sensors in general. The energy consumption and processing requirements (processor, bandwidth, etc.) of multimedia sensors are also considered high, while their battery life duration is considerably shorter than scalar sensors. Finally, the requirement for line of sight in the monitored spaces, which compromises the applicability of multimedia sensors especially in heavily-partitioned spaces.

Clearly, one needs to find a trade-off between multimedia sensors and camera sensors to be adopted in a smart building: *Scalar sensors can provide high precision measurements. The hardware can be cheaper and consume low power. However, they provide very limited information about occupants. Multimedia sensors can detect various kinds of events and occupant activities. However, the detection accuracy can be variable and the intrusiveness can be high and problematic in some cases⁶.*

2.3 Smart devices

Data about occupants is essential for optimizing the performance of building subsystems and processes such as lighting, HVAC, safety, security and facility management. Current scalar sensors can easily provide building data (e.g., temperature, lighting level, relative humidity, etc.) but fall short when providing occupancy data. This is the case for motion detectors since they cannot provide the required granularity of information. Multimedia sensors (such as IP cameras) currently provide the most powerful sensing capability for tracking occupants. Unfortunately, they also have significant

⁶ Nowadays, it is common that a non-residential building is equipped with cameras and microphones for building surveillance. In this case, the intrusiveness aspect is no longer feared. Hence, several events, activities and room occupancies can be detected for a better energy management.

drawbacks as mentioned previously: they are expensive, require a large communications bandwidth for streaming video, and most importantly, they are perceived as privacy invasive.

In order to overcome the limitations of (scalar and multimedia) sensors and the challenges of providing building and occupancy information accurately, reliably, affordably and without violating privacy, several dedicated smart devices have emerged in order to collect other necessary information. The idea is to use smart sensors that perform all analytics on board and output only the processed data. The devices employ deep learning and object tracking algorithms that are streamlined to run effectively on low power processors.

In what follows, we present several dedicated devices provided to collect building occupancy information.

2.3.1 Lensless Smart Sensors (LSS)

Rambus Corporation offers Lensless Smart Sensors (LSS)⁷, a low-power and low-cost sensor technology capable of capturing information-rich images and sensing data in the thermal or visible spectrum. To reduce the cost, the use of traditional visible and thermal lenses has been replaced by tiny and low-cost diffractive optic gratings attached directly to the image sensor array. To reduce the power consumption, gratings and application-specific algorithms are combined with standard visible or thermal sensors and optimized for specific applications. LSS can be used for point tracking, gesture recognition, change detection, and range finding, which match with intended services on smart buildings.

2.3.2 Wearable smart devices

A wearable device refers to an electronic technology or computer that is incorporated into items of clothing and accessories during the realization of daily tasks inside the building. There are several types of wearable devices: watch, wristband, chest straps, etc. To select the proper wearable devices to be used, there are some relevant criteria to be considered:

- *Accuracy*: since the quality of measurement directly affects the quality of the signal analysis. The accuracy highly depends on two main factors:
 - the type of sensor, which can be red infrared light sensor, optical or contact sensors, and
 - the part of the body, where the sensor must be worn, which can be chest straps, arm and finger.
- *Periodicity of monitoring*: since the data analysis requires a minimum set of data in order to guarantee the validity of the analysis.
- *Occupant comfort*: the more comfortable the device is, the more the occupant is engaged to wear it.

Several types of wearable devices are used to monitor health (heart rate, blood pressure, occupant activities, etc.). They can be classified into two categories depending on the signal they send:

- *Continuous monitoring*: sends multiple measures per second, providing a huge amount of

⁷ <https://www.rambus.com/emerging-solutions/lensless-smart-sensors/>

data to be processed, allowing a more complete set of data to get more precision in the analysis, and

- *Synchronization monitoring*: sends one measure per second in the best cases.

The wearable devices covered in the following subsections were chosen since they allow to monitor and sense people activities.

2.3.2.1 Zephyr Bioharness BT

The Zephyr BioHarnes BT is a compact electronics module⁸. The sensor is a contact type connected to the body and located at the chest (as shown in Figure 5) allowing the user to work in a comfortable way. It is attached to a lightweight Smart Fabric strap which incorporates ECG and breathing detection sensors. The measurements supplied by this device are Heart Rate, Breathing Rate, Skin Temperature, Activity, Posture, and Skin Conductance. The BioHarnes module can transmit physiological data with a detailed specification by Bluetooth or by Android java API with direct methods to get measured data. The data can also be recorded in the internal memory of the device or in a continuous way published or stored as needed by third parties applications. The accuracy of the data is high.

Figure 5: Zephyr Bioharness BT

2.3.2.2 Zephyr Bioharness HxM

The Zephyr Bioharness HxM device⁹ is similar to Zephyr BioHarnes BT and used to monitor Heart Rate, speed & distance. The sensor is a contact type connected to the body and located at the chest (as shown in Figure 6). The accuracy of the data is high but in order to work properly it requires some relative humidity constraints in the sensors. The HxM™ BT smart fabric-based strap also provides good comfort and performance, with the potential for easy integration into branded garments.

The data is provided by a java Android API with direct methods to get measurements. The data can be stored directly in the device or in a continuous way published or stored as needed by third party applications.

Figure 6: Zephyr HxM

⁸ <https://www.zephyranywhere.com/>

⁹ <http://www.zephyr-technology.nl/en/product/71/zephyr-bioharness.html>

2.3.2.3 Zephyr Bioharness HxM Smart

The Zephyr Bioharness HxM Smart device¹⁰ is used to monitor Heart Rate, Heart Rate Variability, R-R Interval, Stress Level, Activity Level, Peak Acceleration, Calories. The sensor is a contact type connected to the body and located at the chest (as Zephyr HxM). The accuracy of the data is high, with some relative humidity constraints in the sensors. This device is an evolution of previous models of Zephyr HxM BT and the BioHarness. The HxM™ Smart gives Heart Rate and R-R Interval with Bluetooth Smart (4.0), allowing easy connection with iPhone 5, iPhone 4s, iPod Nano and other Bluetooth Smart Ready devices. The data is available to any application that implements the Bluetooth Low Energy Heart Rate profiles protocol.

The HxM™ BT smart fabric-based strap also provides good comfort and performance, with the potential for easy integration into branded garments.

2.3.2.4 Fitbit Charge HR

The Fitbit Charge HR device¹¹ allows the monitoring of Heart Rate and user activity (steps counter, distance, floors rises, calories and sleep monitoring). This device has other functionalities like Time, notifications, incoming calls from synchronized smartphone. The sensor is based on an optical sensor and is located on the wrist as shown in Figure 7. The accuracy level is high but to work properly it requires some constraints in positioning and the pressure of the wristband in the wrist.

The data is transmitted to any equipment connected by Bluetooth (e.g., computer, smartphone, etc.) with a proprietary application and synchronized with a Fitbit cloud server. This latter capability provides an Open API under the OAuth 2.0 protocol authorization to get data from the device. This is an indirect way to get data. The number of values per second is less than in other devices, which allows direct connection to monitor provided measures.

Figure 7: Fitbit Charge HR

2.3.2.5 Sony Smartband 2 SWR12

The Sony Smartband 2 SWR12 device¹² allows monitoring Heart Rate and user activity like steps counter, distance, and sleeping monitoring. The sensor is optical and located on the wrist as shown in Figure 8. As the Fitbit Charge HR device, the accuracy level is high but to work properly it requires correct positioning to ensure an appropriate pressure contact with the wrist.

¹⁰ <https://www.zephyranywhere.com/resources/hxm>

¹¹ <https://www.fitbit.com/fr/chargehr>

¹² <http://www.sonymobile.com/fr/products/smart-products/smartband-2/>

The data is transmitted by Bluetooth connectivity to a proprietary smartphone application and synchronized with the Sony cloud server LifeLog and also allows integration with GoogleFit API server. In addition with the Sony smartphone application, it is possible to visualize the stress level based on heart rate values. Although this information is not published by the API to third party applications, both LifeLog and GoogleFit provides an Open APIs under OAuth 2.0 protocol authorization to get data from the device. The number of values per second is less than in other devices, which allows direct connection to monitor measures.

Figure 8: Sony Smartband 2 SWR12

2.3.2.6 Smartwatch Moto 360

The Smartwatch Moto 360 device is a smartwatch with the Android Wear operating system. The sensor is an optical heart rate monitor (PPG) located at the back of the watch and with direct contact with the wrist as shown in Figure 9. The data is accessible by the Android Wear API to any Android application.

Figure 9: Moto 360 2nd Generation

2.3.3 Discussion

A summary of the analysed wearable devices is shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Summary of the analysed wearable smart devices

Device	Type Sensor	Position	Connectivity	Data
Zephyr Bioharness BT	Contact	Chest	Bluetooth to smartphone	Zephyr API for Android processed data
Zephyr Bioharness HxM	Contact	Chest	Bluetooth to smartphone	Zephyr API for Android processed data
Zephyr Bioharness HxM Smart	Contact	Chest	Bluetooth to smartphone	Bluetooth Low Energy heart Rate Monitoring Profiles
Fitbit Charge HR	Optical	Wrist	Bluetooth to proprietary app	Data from Fitbit Server via OAuth
Sony Smartband 2 SWR12	Optical	Wrist	Bluetooth to proprietary app	Data from GoogleFit Server via OAuth
Smartwatch Moto 360	Optical	Wrist	Bluetooth	Heart Rate value from Android API sensor

In order to choose a smart device to detect occupant activities, one must consider several parameters:

- *Software Openness*: it is important to choose an operating system that provides an open framework to access the data from the device but also to tune the network protocols. Android looks here a nice choice.
- *Hardware Openness*: it is important to choose a device that allows some extensibility in terms of hardware capabilities (adding memory, plugging new equipment, etc.).
- *Comfort*: it is a must to choose an appropriate device that has less impact on the occupant activities. Here for instance the smart-watches seem to be a good choice.
- *Accuracy*: it is important to also choose the device that is the most suited to complement the requirements of accuracy and periodicity of sensing.
- *Privacy*: it is a must to provide the occupant with a solution that guarantees and secures his/her privacy. This should consider different parameters (age, culture, gender, activities, etc.).

2.4 HIT2GAP sensors

HIT2GAP adopted several sensors for inclusion in its platform and feed of the data post-processing modules (especially the behaviour modelling module). Table 3 shows their main list and gives a small description of each one as well as the related criteria. Although pluggable thanks to its open architecture and data model, HIT2GAP framework does not include multimedia sensors mainly because they have not clearly shown yet their superiority over scalar ones.

Table 3. HIT2GAP sensors

	Sensor	Partner providing the sensor	Short description
Openness	BUILDAX	University Of Strathclyde	BuildAx is an open-source solution for Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ) monitoring. Different from most solutions for pervasive sensing based on proprietary technologies, the key point of BuildAx solution is its open nature. Both hardware and software are published, so any person can further develop monitoring solutions based on them. The integrated nature of BuildAx ENV provides multiple sensors in a single small device, facilitating data collection on several environmental parameters. BuildAx also offers a switch sensor, which is triggered by opening/closing windows (using a small magnet attached to the moving element. This is ideal to monitor some aspects of building operation that are crucial for energy performance analysis.
Accuracy	MM-WSN (Multi Magnitude Wireless Sensor Network)	TEKNIKER	The first version of the MM-WSN was developed within the TIBUCON project, which aimed to reduce energy consumption through the enhancement of the HVAC system performance by increasing the resolution of sensing and actuation points. The technologies produced in TIBUCON have been further developed in order to improve their capabilities (enclosure, autonomy, sensors, etc.) as well as to meet the philosophy promoted by HIT2GAP. The MM-WSN devices provide multiple spatially separated sensing points over the environment and the use of Energy Harvesting and optional battery increases the range of application domains and deployment opportunities. The increased resolution of sensing measurement locations allows a more fine-tuned of the HVAC systems which translates to a more efficient energy consumption management.
Interoperability	WT (Wireless Things)	APINTECH	WT can support a great diversity of wireless data networking. Thanks to the Baseboard module, it can link to any external sensor via a large set of possible interfaces (pulses, analogue, UART, SPI, I2C, etc.). WT also includes monitoring and instrumentation boards. The instrumentation that will be used comprises type basic types of modules: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy modules, for energy / power parameter monitoring • Baseboard modules, for interfacing to any other kind of sensor values (temperature, flows, solar radiation, etc.).
Real-time tracking	Indoor positioning system	EURECAT	The technology provided by EURECAT allows the continuous tracking in real-time of people inside a building with an accuracy of few meters of error, assuming that these people are equipped with mobile devices (e.g., smartphones, smartwatches...) in which the positioning engine software can run. It can enable valuable location-based metrics that can enhance the basic presence detection functionality at the HIT2GAP platform: people counting, people location, people tracking and people detection. These features can be exploited to improve the operation parameters of air conditioning, ventilation or lighting, considering the distribution of people in the areas of influence of each device or even adjusting parameters based on the specific preferences of users. The EURECAT indoor positioning technology requires BLE or Wi-Fi infrastructure deployed inside the building.
Occupant Comfort	'Smartwatch with android Wear' operative system	TEKNIKER	The wearable devices are intended to be used to get indirect inputs from users of the building by analysing the Heart Rate and activity of the occupant.

3 Recent methods and technologies

Various recent methods and technologies are described in the literature to allow better description and detection of building activities such as indoor localization detection, noise detection, etc. They are reviewed in the following subsections.

3.1 Signal processing

Indoor localization is an important facility that should be provided by smart buildings to meet Federal Communications Commission (FCC) regulations (for 911 calls) and for occupants' safety [21]. Despite the availability of Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) and cellular-based methods, indoor positioning remains a difficult problem. Restrictions of both methods are mainly related to the building structure (e.g., producing signal impairments) and to the requirement for each person to carry some compatible device. Recent approaches [22,23] propose to use vibration sensors for measuring occupant-generated vibrations (i.e., vibrations mainly produced by person footsteps). With this new source of information and by extending conventional localization algorithms (to accommodate signal distortions encountered by vibrations in building structures), it will be possible to locate persons moving within a building [21,24]. These approaches also offer a means to detect and locate a person who falls, which is a significant capability in hospitals and assisted living homes.

Audio-based signal processing algorithms have also been used to estimate indoor occupancy (i.e., number of people), due to the rapid advances of technologies to process audio and speech. The idea is to capture the changes of the acoustic properties in a room [25,26].

The measurement of sound waves in a space is an interesting technique that is currently being studied for use in occupancy driven control application in buildings and can be considered as an improvement over PIR sensors as they do not require line of sight and continuous movement [73,77-82]. As building occupants often produce a variety of audible sound waves, its measurement using microphones or Ultrasonic sensors can provide occupancy information on location and presence. Unlike PIR sensors which are passive, ultrasonic sensors are active devices which emit and receive ultrasonic sound waves to and from the environment [79-81]. The sensors are ideally, non-terminal-based and non-individualized, but can be implemented as terminal-based and individualized detection system for other specialized applications [81]. Ultrasonic sensors have also been demonstrated to have the capacity to provide occupancy information on location and presence [73]. As PIR-based systems, ultrasonic sensors use in demand-driven control of HVAC systems is also limited due to the sensor output is binary, hence its inability to provide information on count and they are susceptible to false ON often triggered by vibrations such as the air turbulence from HVAC systems, or even moving paper coming from a printer, and they are susceptible to false OFF when quiet occupants are in the spaces.

Electromagnetic signals (EM) present in the form of wireless fidelity (Wi-Fi), Bluetooth, radio frequency identification tags (RFID) enabled devices are systems also commonly found in commercial office buildings [69, 82-86]. The system is usually composed of a transmitting (usually carried by the user) and a receiving node (usually static), which allows for either the measurement of the energy or timing of the response echo of a transmitted signal by the receiving node. Occupancy detection systems based on the measurement of EM signals have been demonstrated to can provide occupancy information on user location, presence, count, identity, and track. Though having the capability to provide comprehensive fine-grained occupancy information for demand driven applications in buildings, complaints are related to the user privacy, users feel they are constantly

been monitored; the need of connection or association of multiple connected devices to one occupant; and complex and advanced signal processing station is often required.

The approach presented in [25] proposes two estimation occupancy algorithms: (i) in a meeting mode scenario, the audio is recorded through microphones and a speaker recognition system is used to recognize the voice of each speaker in the room, then speakers are counted; and (ii) in a party mode, an important feature of speech, known as Short-Time Energy or STE (i.e., a feature of signal energy among a short interval of time), is used to estimate the number of people. The approach described in [26] is based on measured changes in ultrasonic chirp reflected from a wide-band transmitter and recording how the signal is dissipated over the time. By analyzing the frequency response over the chirp's bandwidth at a few known occupancy levels, the algorithm can extrapolate the response as the number of people in the room.

3.2 Internet of Things (IoT)

Internet of Things (IoT) comprises a network of devices (e.g., sensors, software, and electronics) that are connected to the Internet, integrating greater computer capabilities and using data analytics to extract meaningful information. One of the applications of IoT in the urban context is to smart buildings. IoT technologies enable connected devices to communicate with each other as well as with occupants, allowing for the quick completion of tasks. These Internet-connected devices create, process, and deliver information that can be collected in a central command hub to provide rapid databases with the raw data needed to make decisions.

Many works in this regard [27][28][29][30][31] have realized these benefits of IoT technologies to provide better services for smart buildings, particularly on automation of public buildings for monitoring energy consumption, pollution level, carbon dioxide level, temperature, humidity, pressure, light intensity, etc. Most of these works combine Wi-Fi connectivity with ambient sensors to monitor indoor environments over long periods of time. Some of them use ad-hoc wireless sensor networks and protocols [27][28][29], while others use traditional Zig-Bee wireless networks combined with IoT technologies [30][31]. All of them consider a centralized database to store the remote collected data. IoT-based smart systems allow long period observations, remote data gathering, reactive ambient analysis, and the further processing of historical data.

PointGrab Company offers IoT image-based smart sensors¹³ to provide accurate occupancy information, without violating privacy. This approach combines advanced computer vision with deep learning and object tracking algorithms performed on the image-based smart sensors to do analytics on board and outputs only the processed data -- a kind of a 'picture-less camera'. These algorithms are streamlined to run effectively on low power processors, thus these smart sensors can support applications and use cases such as space utilization (by tracking occupants locations and movements), energy saving (by determining how to optimally light a space while taking advantage of natural light), safety and security (by detecting events such as tailgating and detecting loitering in pre-defined zones), retail analytics (by providing a precise understanding of shoppers activity, including traffic paths).

Ultra-low power communication is one of essential needs of the IoT which can be satisfied using the Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE), the latest radio technology of the Bluetooth Special Interest Group (SIG)¹⁴. This technology has been particularly designed to keep the energy consumption low while providing higher throughput, lower latency, but with a comparatively shorter range (up to 50m). The

¹³ <http://www.pointgrab.com/>

¹⁴ <https://www.bluetooth.com>

low energy consumption would allow sensors to communicate with other devices using a coin cell battery for a time span of up to two years. In the context of smart buildings, BLE solutions (e.g., iBeacon) allow the use of existing smart phone technology to provide much more accurate indoor positioning than traditional Wi-Fi – e.g., (IoT) Location Based Services (LBS). This smart building technology can capture utilization across a space and improve the reliability of user centric micro-location services information. Realizing the significance of LBS, Apple introduced the iBeacons in Worldwide Developers Conference (WWDC) 2013 as part of its iOS 7.0¹⁵. The beacon is the device that emits BLE signals whereas the iBeacon is the Apple proprietary protocol. This technology allows the mobile applications running on either iOS or Android platform to receive these BLE signals, that can be used for identifying proximity as well as provisioning of contextual aware services. Using the occupants' mobile devices as sensors has been validated as an effective solution to have accurate occupancy detection systems. Now with the BLE-based iBeacons technology, it is possible to have accurate and also power efficient methods to identify room occupants of smart buildings using mobile devices as source of information [50-55]. The work presented in [49] proposes a modification of the iBeacon protocol to change the way the beacons advertise the region associated with them. In the original iBeacon protocol, each beacon correlates only a single region. The authors in [49] adapt iBeacon to allow beacons advertise more than one region, thus every time a beacon changes the region advertised, the device will receive a notification as the ones received when it enters in a new region. In such a way, it is possible to gather and process information about the beacons movements (thus identifying and tracking them) inside the building, to realize an occupancy detection system characterized by high levels of accuracy and power efficiency.

To sum up, most of these works combine IoT technologies with well-known concepts such as: Wireless Sensor Networks (e.g., temperature and relative humidity sensors, a light sensors, microcontrollers, wireless transceivers), custom and adapted algorithms to collect and aggregate data (e.g., voting algorithms, information systems), database systems (e.g., MySQL, Postgres, Data Warehouses), reasoning and context awareness to make decisions, and mobile applications to monitor data remotely (e.g., Android applications, smartphones applications).

3.3 Crowd-sourcing/sensing and Big Data

“Crowd-sourcing/sensing” is an evolving approach to collect massively environmental or behavioural data from a population, emerged along with the rapid emergence of mobile devices. It involves a large and diffuse group of participants in the task of retrieving reliable data from the environment, to be used in multiple research studies, such as traffic and road monitoring, urban mobility, social networking, environmental monitoring, and the study of sociocultural attitudes [42].

Several projects have been proposed to support the development and experimentation of crowd-sourcing/sensing based applications:

- The Inria ADAM project team has developed APISENSE [43-45], a distributed crowdsensing platform based on the principles of Cloud computing to offer a modular service-oriented architecture, targeting multiple research communities. APISENSE provides a lightweight solution to build and deploy crowd-sensing applications for collecting and offering realistic activity traces as experimental datasets. This project also proposes a high-level programming model to get rid of the complexity associated with the development of mobile data collection applications. In the context of smart buildings, APISENSE is still a platform for scientific research used for experimental simulations.

¹⁵ <http://www.odysseyinc.com/blog/i Beacons-revolutionize-location-based-notifications/> – <https://developer.apple.com/ibeacon/>

- IoT Lab [46] is a recent European funded project proposing the idea of Testbed as a Service (TBaaS), available to the research community, as an extension to the traditional IoT testbed infrastructures, to support the design, implementation, and testing of crowd-sensing based solutions. Using a smart phone application, the crowd can participate in experiments by contributing with sensory data and knowledge. The IoT Lab platform leverages the IoT ARM (architecture reference model) design framework to create an initial architecture that includes virtualization of crowdsourcing and testbed components as well as ability to federate with other testbeds. The aim is to develop a crowdsourcing infrastructure together with the supporting mechanisms that will enable multidisciplinary experimentation with a focus on IoT and multidisciplinary experiments including social and economic dimensions.

In the context of smart buildings, this technology starts to gain attention for emergency managing [47] and for indoor localization [48]. In [47], a Danger-System is provided for detection and management of emergencies in smart buildings. Danger-System exploits the existing building management systems leveraging mobile crowd sensing to collect valuable information during a crisis and capable to detect false alarms and to provide context-dependent notification. A quite good survey of works related to indoor location based on crowd-sensing is presented in [48]. Also, smart buildings are composed of systems and devices that produce a huge amount of data related to building management (e.g., temperature and relative humidity levels), access control (e.g., occupancy statistics), as well as other measurements. Once all these kinds of data are collected, they can be combined and modelled to adjust seasonality, measurement scales, and other factors that may skew the findings. Hence, to support smart buildings, high-speed analytics are necessary to aggregate that information and here come also the opportunities of Big Data [32]. Big data technologies would allow the analysis and visualization of large and complex data sets to provide insightful conclusions. Sensor data streams, with analytics applied in real time, offer significant potential for just-in-time service delivery and cost savings. In a Big Data platform, the data flowing from connected sensors is captured to allow easy storage and search of large data volumes; it enables insights for patterns and correlations. Such analysis can be used to improve traditional services for smart buildings (e.g., energy savings, fault detection, automatic HVAC control, workplace optimization, etc.), and in some cases, to generate business intelligence [33-34]. Some examples of what is possible with Big Data technologies in smart buildings are: (i) rightsizing of service delivery by just-in-time triggering of work orders based on people activity, frequency of utilization, events, alarms, and needs; (ii) improved occupant satisfaction through pro-active interventions; (iii) energy savings through tuning of installations; and (iv) improved building performance by detecting trends and patterns in the collected data.

Beyond research projects on the integration of IoT and Big Data technologies in smart buildings, nowadays there exist a bench of companies that offer new related facilities. For example, MCS Corporation¹⁶ provides an output/outcome-based collaborative model to predict cleaning services (cleaning service is no longer executed per fixed schedules but targeted where they are most needed, without wasting time or resources). This service consists of wireless sensor networks, real-time data analytics, and direct communication with field workers and end occupants through mobile applications, dashboards, and kiosks. Collected data is related to occupancy, reservations, weather conditions, measurements of cleaning results (output-based information) as well as previous cleaning results, impact on occupants, and occupant satisfaction tracking (outcome-based information). By correlating this data, predictive cleaning is possible, bringing to building managers facilities to deploy resources most effectively and to cleaners' facilities to provide most efficient services.

¹⁶ <https://www.mcsolutions.com>

It is important to note that the state-of-the-art is still in an early stage of development and lacks reusable solutions for safely collecting and exploiting crowd activity traces and big data analysis. Moreover, the big challenges of these applications are related to privacy, security, energy save, and heterogeneity of mobile platforms.

3.4 Social sensors

In accordance with the recent remarkable growth of smart devices, Social Networks (SNs) are shifting rapidly to a mobile-first strategy. Gartner has reported that users can choose a smartphone or a tablet as their first computing device instead of a PC [35]. Smart mobile devices have various types of sensors. Among them, the most noteworthy is Global Positioning System (GPS) able to observe a location of a mobile device.

SNs and GPS-enabled mobile devices have brought about a paradigm shift in the Internet. Location information of SN users is often given as check-in and geotagged information. Check-in is an innovation used by geo-social platforms, such as Facebook and Google+, enabling users to report their location as a check-in. Geotag is metadata consisting of at least the latitude and longitude of the user's location. It is stored with various media, such as photographs, videos, and Tweets. They are commonly called Social Sensors.

Social sensor data can be considered as a nice means to observe and detect people activities and events within the building. For example, an occupant might tweet "I'm having lunch at home since it's raining!" allowing, after analysis, to identify his location, activity and the weather outside. This event detection need in SNs has emerged in several studies (natural phenomenon, profile detection, drawing maps, etc.). Sakaki et al. [36] proposed keyword-based models using Twitter to automatically identify where and when earthquakes occur. Yamaguchi et al. [37] used a large Twitter dataset to infer users' home locations. Crandall et al. [39] proposed a mapping system using a combination of textual and visual features from a large photographic database that was crawled from Flickr. Ruocco et al. [38] used Suffix Tree Clustering to discover events and their occurrence time and position from Flickr photographs.

To sum up, it becomes interesting to combine physical and social sensors in order to better detect occupant activities. The most advantage of social sensors is that data are driven and given by users allowing to easily and more efficiently detect some events and objects that physical sensors cannot always detect (e.g., a security camera cannot recognize the most favourite food of a person in the video but a social sensor can deliver this information in a better way). Social sensors are promising to come up with a rich Human-Building Interaction (HBI) in a smart building environment.

4 Conclusions

Improving the energy efficiency of buildings is an important step towards a more sustainable lifestyle, leading to significant cost savings and better usage of resources. Smart buildings rely on many sensors and actuators placed at different locations. Reducing the energy consumption requires continuous monitoring of various environmental parameters inside and outside the building. The key requirement for an efficient monitoring and controlling is not only related to all sensors and actuators in the building network but also and mainly the occupants.

Existing solutions attempt to reduce energy consumed by different equipment such as HVAC, lighting, home and office appliances. However, more energy can be saved when the different building subsystems cooperate with each other and monitoring of occupant activities and building events is in the loop. For example, office lights can be switched off, the heating can be lowered, and an employee's PC switched to standby mode when the employee has left the building.

In this report, we studied the different existing solutions provided to monitor building equipment (HVAC, lighting, etc.) through scalar sensors and actuators. We also explored solutions related to multimedia sensors, which enable to monitor the occupant behaviour in a better way. We witnessed how new generation of dedicated sensors is emerging to better detect occupant activities in a building.

To complete the whole picture, we also presented several recent methods related to signal processing, IoT technologies, crowdsourcing and Big Data analysis, and social sensing. The advantage of these methods is that they allow easy and more accurate detection of the occupant behaviour and events.

Our conclusions concerning the application of these technologies to the HIT2GAP project is that several existing solutions can cope with some requirements related to the occupant behaviour and activity detection. HIT2GAP adopts several interesting sensors delivered by the partners able to provide accurate and open sensing from building and occupants (see Table 3 for more details). HIT2GAP will implement also a set of methods in which recent methods and technologies are considered mainly Big Data analysis (through a set of advanced services to be provided to end-users such as energy prediction, anomaly detection, etc.). However, there are several main issues and perspectives to explore in the future in order to see how to inject them into HIT2GAP scope:

- How to help deploy sensors and sensor networks in a building in order to detect all the requested events and activities?
- How to exploit Big Data analysis in restricted environments (since several buildings won't have enough processing and storage capacities to exploit collected data)?
- What's the list of events and activities to detect in a building which can play a major role in energy optimization? And how to make this list evolve with the building life?
- How to cope with the privacy of occupants while looking for more precision in event detection?

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6 Glossary and Acronyms

API	Application Programming Interface
BAS	Building Automation System
BLE	Bluetooth Low Energy
BMS	Building Management System
BOD	Building Occupancy Detection
EGC	Electrocardiography
EM	ElectroMagnetic
EPLM	Electric Plug Loads Management
FCC	Federal Communications Commission
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite Systems
GPS	Global Positioning Systems
HAS	Home Automation System
HBI	Human-Building Interaction
HR	Heart Rate
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation and Air-Conditioning
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IoT	Internet of Things
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
LBS	Location Based Services
LED	Light-Emitting Diode
LIU	LIUPPA
LSS	Lensless Smart Sensors
MFCC	Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients
MSN	Multimedia Sensor Network
PC	Personal Computer
PIR	Passive Infrared
RFID	Radio Frequency IDentification
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
SN	Social Network
SPO2	Saturation of Peripheral Oxygen
STE	Short-Time Energy
SVM	Support Vector Machine
TEK	IK4-Tekniker
WSN	Wireless Sensor Network